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**REAL ESTATE REGULATION AND DEVELOPMENT BILL
2016: INSIGHT REVIEW & IMPACT ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

Real estate sector is traditionally unregulated and unorganized sector in India. There were no established guidelines on most of the aspects and builders use this weakness to make maximum out of the situation and exploit buyers. The real estate prices have crossed the level that it has become extremely difficult for a common man to fulfill its basic need of having his own house. In this scenario, the real estate regulations are not just a requirement, but a big need of the hour, if our economy and society needs some stability in long run. In this paper, Era of pre Real Estate Bill, Need & Evolution of Bill, various dimensions of Regulatory framework and Major aspects of Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Bill, 2015 are being examined. While on one hand, this bill addresses various issues that will help the industry, on the other hand this bill still have many loopholes which can be exploited by the builders.

Keywords: Real Estate Bill, India, Regulation, Industry

INTRODUCTION

The real estate sector in India has been largely unregulated and opaque, with distressed consumers, builders and developers who are unable to have complete information, or enforce accountability against each other in the absence of effective regulation in place. Land laws have become redundant as they were static over more than a century and not been upgraded with time. The real estate industry despite its mammoth size did not have a regulator to regulate and balance the interests of the developers on one hand and the consumers on the other hand. It also lacks transparency with respect to the nature of project, size, cost and the timely completion of the project. No guidelines were framed stating the duties of the developer to the consumer. Allegations about charging exorbitant prices, delay in completing the project or abandoning the project were frequently made against some of the builders. The consumers had to sign on the dotted line of builder buyer agreement, while the builder reserved the right to change the terms of the agreement with ease. The common consumer suffered silently, those who challenged had to take recourse to Consumer Courts. For a long time a need has been felt to regulate and organise the sector. The last few years have seen enormous rise in the sector and real estate prices have increased tremendously. There has been an increase in foreign investment as well. Hence, some new legislations are sought to be enacted, which will affect the real estate industry in a big way.

The Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Bill 2016, is an important move by the Government of India to curb the irregularities and increase transparency in this sector. It is an attempt to make builders accountable and ensure transparent dealings. It is essential that the present issues be properly addressed so as to contribute to real estate sector's growth. It will also ensure land transfers safer and transparent. Since the first draft of Real Estate Regulatory Bill introduced, many amendments were done over the time to make it more effective. This bill will keep the scrupulous developer at bay and secondly sooner than later it will push sale of the developed land/flats. It also has provisions for setting up a regulator for the real estate sector and also imprisonment up to three years for developers who make offences like giving misleading promotions about projects repeatedly.

The Real Estate Bill 2016 seeks to establish an authority to regulate, control and promote development, bring transparency, protection of customer's interest and to facilitate speeding up the construction and timely possession. The Bill calls for strict disclosure norms and compulsory registration for every new housing project. The legislation aims at a major turnaround of the real estate sector while restricting unfair practices. However it is essential that the concerns of the industry, consumers & other stakeholders are also addressed and suitable improvements be incorporated through necessary amendments into the bill in due course.

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK IN REAL ESTATE – DIMENSIONS & APPLICABILITY

There are various activities involved in formalising a real estate project. The activities start from conceptualising a project to land identification & acquisition and lasts till possession & transfer of ownership. Various dimensions and areas where the regulatory framework is applicable are briefly tabulated as below:

Sr. No.	Dimensions	Applicability
1	Land	Identification
		Acquisition
		Change of Land Use (CLU)
		Compensation to owners
		Ownership
		Right of Way (ROW)
2	Classification	Zoning of Land
		Residential/Industrial/Commercial
		Mix Use
		Agriculture
		Forest
3.	Sale of Real Estate	Free hold
		Lease & Hire basis
		Power of Attorney
		Transfer
4	Construction Modes	Builder Buyer Agreement
		Construction Link Plan
		Group Construction

		Ready to Move in
5	Establishment /Entity	Co-operative Group Housing Society
		Welfare Group Housing Society
		Govt. Housing Scheme
		Individual ownership
6	Financing	Financial Closure
		Line of Credit
		Soft loans/ Loan
		Approval of banks & Fin. Institutions

EVOLUTION OF REAL ESTATE BILL- NEED OF THE HOUR

With the sudden increase in demand and steep rise in prices during last decade, there has been a mushroom growth of project developers, real estate companies, brokers/ consultants/ estate agents and financial institutions. This era of sudden growth in the sector has caused a turbulent atmosphere in the market and property sector was being considered as one of the most preferred source of investment & return oriented. This has also motivated common man to invest their own & outsourced funds in property sector. With the presence of unorganised players, inexperienced professionals and lack of effective regulatory framework, there has been number of instances where the commitment made by one stakeholder was not fulfilled towards other.

Over the time, voices have been raised from all stakeholders whether it is consumer, developers, financial institutions, land owners or suppliers, to safeguard their interest. All of them have raised their voice at every doorstep of Judiciary, Executive, Legislative, Law enforcement agencies and even to media, when the hard earned money of stakeholders is getting stuck due to unfair practices or otherwise.

This environment has created a factor of fear, unrest, lack of trust towards economy and business environment of country. At the same time credibility of Government & Citizens trust in administration was on stake. With the intervention of Courts, strengthening the voice of people through media and demand by industrial & consumer forums, Government has recognised the pulse of people & need of the hour. It is year 2010 when Govt. has taken first step towards formalising the Real Estate Regulatory Bill, constituted a committee to examine the matter and did stake holders consultation through various means. Subsequently, first draft of Real Estate Regulatory Bill was released in 2013 and thereafter it was finalised by both houses of Parliament in 2016.

THE MAJOR HIGHLIGHTS OF REAL ESTATE BILL ARE AS FOLLOWS

1. Applicability of this bill- Initially the bill was applicable to residential real estate only. Now, the Cabinet has stretched the applicability of the Bill to commercial real estate also. Ongoing projects that have not got Completion Certificates have also been come under the purview of this Bill. Further, such projects will need to be registered with the regulator.
2. Mandatory to acquire all clearances before the launch - In the proposed bill, it would be mandatory for the developers/builders to acquire all the required clearances from relevant authorities and government bodies before formally launching the project. In recent past builders launch the project when there is nothing on the site and do not have requisite approvals. They present rosy pictures to investors, start collecting funds from customers and then start the overall process of acquiring the land, getting approvals, and coming up with the structure. This creates frustration among investors and delay in completion of projects.

3. Use of photograph of actual site during advertisements - For advertisements of the project, the builders will have to use the actual site pictures or the real construction work pictures. In present scenario, builders do not use the actual pictures for promotional purpose. It is easy to create an illusion by using graphics and shiny pictures full of greenery and nature around it. It gives the feeling that it's an opportunity one should not miss. However, in reality the project site is somewhat different. It happens quite often that the picture shown in sale brochure or in newspaper ads doesn't resemble with the actual site condition.
4. Sale of property as per prices linked with carpet area - The bill says that any sale proceedings should use the prices which are linked with carpet area and not super built up area. Generally, builders use "super built up area" as the parameter and define the per sq.ft. price according to them. Carpet area is the net usable area which is used for living however in addition to net usable area super built up area includes area covered by walls, doors, parking area, staircases, temple inside the project, gym, garden etc. which is part of the package purchased by the buyer. As super built up area becomes high and per sq.ft. price appears low, so the builders quote their price only on super built up area. However, only carpet area is mentioned even in sale agreements.
5. State level regulators and central appellate tribunal to be set up - A two-tier dispute resolution mechanism is suggested which comprises of a Real Estate Regulatory Authority (to act as the nodal agency to co-ordinate efforts regarding development of the real estate sector and render necessary advice to the appropriate Government to ensure the growth and promotion of a transparent, efficient and competitive real estate sector), adjudicating officers at state-level and a central Real Estate Appellate Tribunal to judge upon matters relating to residential projects covered under the Act. Till now, real estate transactions are largely governed by the agreements between the parties, with remedies including specific relief (if applicable) and damages for breach available under civil and criminal law. Pursuant to enactment of the proposed legislation, civil courts will not have any say in respect of any matter covered under the Act. However, real estate regulator can't help much in case title of a land is disputed and builder has bought into the project. The buyer will be the sufferer in such case.
6. Real agents/dealers need to register themselves – In recent past, real estate agents and dealers are not necessary registered with central/state body. Thus, they do not follow any code of conduct or service standards. Now they will have to register themselves and will have clear responsibilities and functions. It is the duty of the real estate agents to maintain books of accounts, records and documents and not to involve in any unfair trade practices. Also, the bill recommends the registration of developers, their projects and their real estate agents with the authority to approve and monitor projects. This bill will bring accountability of dealers/agents and consumers can also demand their rights from agents & dealers for the amount of commissions paid to them.
7. Separate bank accounts for every project - As per the bill, builder will have to maintain separate bank account for each and every project. Also, it has to keep up to 50% of the funds of the project in the same bank account. Usually, when builder faces a severe cash crunch, he launches a new project and uses the money collected in new projects to complete the old projects and this cycle goes on which leads to huge delays at times.
8. Builders can't take more than 10% advance without a written agreement - A builder shall not be able to take more than 10% advance money from buyers without a written agreement. Currently now a lot of dealings materialize by paying huge advances at initial stage even before the written agreement because lots of transactions happen on trust basis. Agreement happens many months or years after initial payment.
9. Full refund with interest, if property not handed over time - As per the bill, the builder will have to refund the money along with the interest, if he fails to deliver the project on time. Earlier, this

point is generally omitted in the agreement by the builders. Customer has no option except to file a consumer court to get his right. However, this bill will make it a standard rule or clause.

10. Adherence to approved plans – Developers have to stick to approved plans and project specifications and are also liable to put right any major structural defect or poor workmanship in the unit, for the promised duration of warranty/after sale services at their own cost. If developers fail to do so within a reasonable time, they shall be liable to pay suitable damages or compensation to the buyers as may be decided by the Authority. Promoters will not be allowed to change plans and structural designs without the prior consent of 2/3rd of consumers of a project.
11. Transparency-Developers would be required to make available information and documents to prospective buyers to bring transparency in development of the proposed project such as master plan of area, layout plans, structural drawings and designs, material specifications and construction schedule, etc. Also, all information regarding project management, project details, schedule of development works, statutory approvals regarding change of land use, development licenses, builder-buyer agreements, names and addresses of sale channel partners, architects and consultants etc. is also required to be disclosed.
12. The bill applies to project over 4,000 sq. meters in size - This bill is applicable only to projects which are of 4,000 sq. meters and above size overall. If a project is bigger than 4,000 sq. meters, the bill permits to break the whole project into different phases and each phase can be seen as different project.
13. No single window clearance for approvals - Builders have raised the issue of single window clearance from a very long time. Getting government clearances and various approvals takes lot of time and opens up the gate for bribes and bureaucracy. This bill has failed to address this problem at all. A separate government department having a single window clearance will address the issue of project completion time more effectively.

TABULATED EVALUATION OF BILL PROVISIONS AND THEIR IMPACT

Provisions	Impact
Mandatory to Acquire All Clearances Before The Launch	As a result, the practice of “soft/pre-launch” offers shall curb. All permissions are also to be displayed on the website of the developer. However, this might slowdown the supply side because earlier builder keeps on launching new projects. On the other hand, buyers will not feel cheated if there is any flaw in the project since clearance will be granted only when all requirements get fulfilled.
Use of Photograph of Actual Site for Advertisements	This is of great help for buyers. There will be no cheating on account of rosy pictures.
Sale of Property As Per Prices Linked With Carpet Area	Per sq. feet rate will shoot up high to negatively influence the mindset of Indian customers.

State Level Regulators and Central Appellate Tribunal to be Set Up	Buyers will get their grievances addressed very fast.
Real Agents/Dealers Needs to Register Themselves	This will empower customers to get appropriate documentation and possession services with greater fairness and transparency.
Separate Bank Accounts For Every Project	This provision will enforce financial discipline, transparency and accountability of the funds deposited by the customers for particular project. However, effectiveness of this provision depends on its enforcement. Even if there is an escrow account, it is difficult to know if it is being used for construction alone. Sanctity of expenses done for particular project or an activity is difficult to ascertain.
Builders Can't Take More Than 10% Advance Without a Written Agreement	Good for buyers as reasonable amount of money is transferred to builders in place of huge funds on finalization of agreement as compared to project progress.
Full Refund With Interest, If Property Not Handed Over Time	Buyers will get compensation if delay happens in possession of property.
Adherence To Approved Plans	Great for users. Builders are often known to hand over projects with a different area than otherwise applicable, or with a wall that's no longer there, or such. Customers will not feel cheated with this provision
Transparency	The buyers will be exposed to all information relating to project. Developers can't cheat them easily.
The Bill Rules Applies To Project Over 4,000 Sq. Meters In Size	This clause itself destroys the protection layer for consumers. Builder can always break the whole project into different phases and show them as separate project. Many builders anyways run various projects under different companies name (which are actually just one project side by side)to save on tax.

No Single Window Clearance For Approvals	This takes a lot of time and opens up the gate for bribes and red-tapism.
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CONCLUSION

The real estate and housing sector has been largely unregulated and opaque, with consumers often being unable to get complete information and hence failed to enforce accountability against builders and developers in the absence of effective regulation. There was a dire need of regulations to have a check on unfair practices of builders. However, the effectiveness of the regulatory Bill depends on how successfully the housing sector issues viz. standardization of sale agreements, efficacy in resolution of complaints and encouragement of private equity through effective regulations are enforced. The government's role in regulating the growth of the real estate housing sector along with the cooperation extended by the major players also plays an important role. Though this bill is a blessing for real estate customers, it has however received much criticism from developers for not addressing their long pending issues. Not only the developer but all stakeholders like brokers, contractors and architects should be made accountable. To what extent this bill has achieved its objectives; this will become clear only when the bill shall be enforced in letter and spirit and by incorporating suitable amendments as a result of experience gained by all stakeholders.

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